

Dispersion of Active Component on Carrier Materials : NiO-Al₂O₃ Catalyst

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For evaluation of dispersion method of active component in carrier materials, studies have been made on alumina supported nickel oxide catalyst. For this purpose three catalysts have been prepared. The dispersion of nickel oxide has been done by (i) hydrolysis of nickel amino complex (ii) precipitation (iii) impregnation methods. It has been observed that the dispersion of nickel oxide is most uniform when the catalyst has been prepared by the hydrolysis of nickel amino complex. The crystallite size of nickel oxide and other structural parameters are better compared to other two samples and also to a standard commercial catalyst.

IT is a major problem in catalytic chemistry to use the precious materials in optimum percentage at the same time with requisite structural and textual parameters as well as higher catalytic activity. For catalytic reaction, quantity of active component is not a main feature but main aspect is the availability of higher active surface with minimum percentage of active component. Higher surface can be obtained in case of mixed oxide system if the active component is uniformly dispersed on a suitable carrier having smaller crystallite size. The technique of dispersion of an active component in a suitable carrier has been used in catalyst preparation for a long time especially when the percentage of the active component is low.

Various methods of preparation for the dispersion of nickel oxide have been employed¹. In all the preparative methods, the sole aim is to disperse the active component uniformly so that the distribution of particle size is achieved in the lowest possible range on support material. Earlier workers have reported the use of amino complexes for the dispersion of metal particles in carrier¹⁻⁴. But no attempt has so far been made to disperse metal oxide by using amino complexes. Transitional metal amino complexes are susceptible to decompose with the change in environmental conditions⁵. In view of the present day trend of the use of metal oxides as an active component in catalyst, an attempt has been made to evaluate a process for better dispersion of metal oxides in the case of mixed oxide catalysts by the hydrolysis of amino complexes. In the present work, study has been made for the dispersion of nickel oxide on alumina carrier.

Experimental

A. Preparation of samples

I. Preparation of NiO

For the purpose of investigation, NiO were prepared by five different methods, and designated as A, B, C, D and E.

Sample A

Nickel amino complexes (prepared by adding excess of ammonia to nickel nitrate solution) was added slowly

to hot water with constant mechanical stirring. The water was taken 30 times to that of amino complex. Ni concentration in the complex was 10% by wt. After digestion for half an hour, the precipitate was washed, oven dried at 120° and finally cured at 500° for 4 hr.

Sample B

Nickel nitrate solution (10%) was treated with dilute ammonia solution for complete precipitation, the precipitated mass was washed with water and oven dried at 120° and finally cured at 500° for 4 hr.

Sample C

Nickel nitrate solution (10%) was treated with dilute ammonium carbonate solution for complete precipitation. The precipitated mass was washed with water, and oven dried at 120° and finally cured at 500° for 4 hr.

Sample D

NiO has been prepared by the thermal decomposition of nickel formate at 500°.

Sample E

NiO has been prepared by the thermal decomposition of Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O at 500°

II. Dispersion of NiO on alumina carrier

For comparison sake, three samples designated by A₁, B₁ and E₁ were prepared by three different methods.

A₁ 90 g. of α-Al₂O₃ powder were taken in dispersed stage in 3 litres of water. Nickel amino complex (100 ml.) was added gradually with constant stirring to the hot suspension of aluminium oxide in water. After digestion for 30 min. the slurry was filtered, washed, oven dried at 120° and finally cured at 500°.

B₁ Nickel hydroxide was precipitated from a solution of nickel nitrate (100 ml) with an aqueous solution of ammonia in the presence of 90 g. carrier alumina dispersed in 2 litres of water at 50°. The precipitate on the carrier was filtered, washed thoroughly and calcined at 500° for 4 hr.

E₁ 90 gms. of α-Al₂O₃ pellets were impregnated with a solution of nickel nitrate (100 ml) and then dried in an air oven at 120° and finally calcined at 500° for 4 hr.

In all the three samples, percentage of NiO was maintained about 10% in the finished product.

Chemical Analysis: The percentage of NiO in sample A₁, B₁ and E₁ were determined gravimetrically using dimethyl-glyoxime as reagent⁶. All the chemicals used in this work were of A. R. quality grade.

B. X-ray diffraction analysis

X-ray diffraction photographs of all the samples were taken in a standard Guinier camera using crystal reflected monochromatic CuK_α radiation, X-ray tube being operated at 40 KV and 20 mA. The d-spacings were measured with the help of a standard Guinier scale. The phases were determined by comparing the observed patterns with standard ASTM patterns⁷.

The crystallite size was determined by line broadening methods using the Scherrer formula⁸.

The crystallite size of nickel oxide in samples A, B, C, D & E were determined along the directions perpendicular to 111, 200, 220, 222 and 400 planes and in samples A₁, B₁ & E₁ along the directions perpendicular to the 111, 200 & 220 planes on the Phillips X-ray diffractometer. PW1050/51.

C. Electron Microscopic Analysis

The samples were first soaked in acetone to remove entrapped air. On drying, these were transferred to a bath of monomer consisting of 4 parts of n-butyl methacrylate and 1 part of n-methyl methacrylate and finally embedded in the polymerised methacrylate using gelatin capsules. Ultra thin sections of thickness ranging from 500 to 800 Å were cut with Cambridge ultramicrotome using a diamond knife. Electron micrographs were obtained with Siemens Elmiskop IA using double condenser illumination to minimise heating.

Surface area: Surface area for the samples A₁, B₁ and E₁ was determined with the help of nitrogen adsorption isotherm at liquid nitrogen temperature by applying B.E.T. equation⁹.

Results

Crystal Phase composition and crystallite size of NiO: The crystal phase composition of all the samples has been shown in Table 1. The crystallite sizes of NiO prepared from different sources by thermal decomposition has been shown in Table 2.

The crystallite size of NiO in NiO-Al₂O₃ system in samples A₁, B₁ & E₁ has been shown in Table 3. The crystallite sizes of NiO along other planes could not be measured due to the superimposition of the diffraction line of α-Al₂O₃ and NiAl₂O₄ on NiO diffraction pattern.

Particle size and Pore size: The particle sizes of NiO in samples A₁, B₁ & E₁ and also mean pore

TABLE 1—CRYSTAL PHASE COMPOSITION

Name of the samples	Curing temperature in °C	Crystalline phases present
A	120±10 500	Ni(OH) ₂ NiO
B	120±10 500	Ni(OH) ₂ NiO ₈ , Ni(OH) ₂ (trace)
C	120±10 500	NiCO ₃ ·6H ₂ O NiO
D	R.T. 500	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O NiO
E	R.T. 500	Ni(C ₂ H ₂ O ₄) ₂ ·2H ₂ O NiO
A ₁	120±10 500	α-Al ₂ O ₃ , Ni(OH) ₂ , NiO (trace) α-Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄ (trace)
B ₁	120±10 500	α-Al ₂ O ₃ , Ni(OH) ₂ , NiO (trace) α-Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄ (trace)
E ₁	120±10 500	α-Al ₂ O ₃ , Ni(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O NiO (trace) α-Al ₂ O ₃ , NiO, NiAl ₂ O ₄

TABLE 2—CRYSTALLITE SIZE (Å) OF NiO PREPARED BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Name of the samples	Planes perpendicular to which crystallite sizes measured				
	111	200	220	222	400
A	130	120	160	95	90
B	180	145	155	95	95
C	160	130	160	100	95
D	270	350	430	280	250
E	390	380	460	360	310

TABLE 3—CRYSTALLITE SIZE OF NiO IN UNSUPPORTED (A, B and E) NiO AND SUPPORTED NiO SYSTEM (A₁, B₁, AND E₁)

Planes perpendicular to which crystallite sizes measured.	Crystallite size in					
	A	B	E	A ₁	B ₁	E ₁
111	130	180	390	60	130	230
200	120	145	380	70	110	160
220	160	155	460	120	160	210

TABLE 4—PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF THE SAMPLE A₁, B₁ AND E₁

Name of the sample	%NiO	Particle size in Å		Average pore diameter in Å	Surface area m ² /gm
		Electron microscopy	X-ray line broadening		
A ₁	9.52	30-40	60	25	41.54
B ₁	9.65	40-120	130	50	34.93
E ₁	9.82	60-210	230	70	30.42

diameter as measured from electron micrographs and the surface area as measured by B.E.T. method are shown in Table 4. In case of Sample A₁, the dispersion is most uniform and clustering is barely noticeable whereas in sample E₁, the dispersion is less uniform and clustering is apparent; interparticle distance is also larger as is observed from electron microscopic results. The shape of the particles in sample A₁ is not distinguishable because of the small particle size whereas in the sample E₁, the major part of the particles appears as square shape and various particles of needle shape are also visible (dimension 0.1μ long). These needle shaped particles are presumed to be nickel aluminate¹⁰.

In the sample B₁ the dispersion is between sample A₁ and E₁. The clustering is prevalent. The bigger nickel oxide particles are seen to have nearly square shape whereas for smaller particles, the shape is not well defined.

In sample A₁, the smaller pores of average diameter nearly 25 Å seem to be more populous. In sample B₁, apart from bigger pores of average diameter 50 Å, still smaller pores of diameter 25 Å are also visible. In sample E₁, the pore diameter is maximum (70 Å) and the distribution is more or less uniform. The particle size of standard nickel-alumina catalyst found to be in the range 50-100 Å.

Discussion

It is known that the structural properties of a solid catalyst play an important role in determining the activity and stability of a catalyst¹¹⁻¹⁵. It is also known that the structural characteristics are influenced by methods of preparation¹⁶. It may be worth-while to discuss the effect of preparative conditions on the structural parameter of NiO-Al₂O₃ samples.

It has been reported earlier¹⁷ that the presence of spinel components makes a catalyst more stable in some catalytic reaction. In that respect all the samples A₁, B₁, E₁ contain NiAl₂O₄ in varying quantities satisfying the condition of suitability. The formation of NiAl₂O₄ is enhanced to some extent in case of sample prepared by soaking (E₁) as compared to samples prepared by precipitated methods (B₁ and A₁). The formation of nickel aluminate in the sample E₁ has also been detected in electron micrograph. It has been noticed that NiAl₂O₄ phase is formed only above 900° in the case of mechanical mixture of NiO and α-Al₂O₃.

In case of pure NiO, the crystallite size is smaller when it is prepared by the hydrolysis of nickel ammino complex than that prepared by the other methods. The formation of smaller crystallite size may be explained on the basis of the hydrolysis of each molecule of nickel ammino complex. Each molecule of [Ni(NH₃)₆](NO₃)₂ decomposes to one molecule of nickel hydroxide in presence of excess water molecules, whereas in the case of precipitation method there is a competition of Ni⁺² to react with added ammonia molecules. In the vicinity of added ammonia molecules a large number of Ni⁺² ions are present and reacting simultaneously with ammonia molecules thereby forming the larger agglomerates of nickel hydroxide and enhancing the crystallite size of NiO in cured samples. Another reason also may be due to the high dilution effect in the case of hydrolysis of [Ni(NH₃)₆](NO₃)₂.

The crystallite size of dispersed NiO is much lowered when it is prepared by the hydrolysis of nickel ammino complex in presence of alumina carrier (Table 3). The diminution in crystallite size in 111 plane is from 130 Å to 60 Å whereas this diminution is only from 180 Å to 130 Å when precipitation method is followed for the same. The crystallite size of NiO is maximum when the impregnation method is followed. This is also

supported by the particle size measurements from electron micrographs. The crystallite size of NiO in NiO-Al₂O₃ system is also comparatively lower along the two other measured planes 200 and 220 (Table 3).

Many authors¹⁸⁻¹⁹ have studied the dependence of specific reaction rate upon particle size. Van Hardeveld et al²⁰ found a clear indication of an effect of the metal particle size on the properties of a metal-on-carrier catalyst. Hardeveld et al²¹ also noted that the crystallites with diameter in the range 15 and 70 Å approximately exhibit a relatively larger number of special sites and also these sites are much less prevalent on crystallites outside this range. The same observation has been noted by Poltorak²². Puri et al²³ have also observed the dependence of catalytic activity on the crystallite size of nickel oxide in steam naphtha reformation catalyst. It appears therefore the crystallite size has got a marked influence on catalytic activity which in turn dependent of the mode of incorporation of the active components in the carrier materials. The catalytic activity is enhanced when the crystallite-size of the active component lies in the range 10-70 Å due to the prevalence of some special sites.

Considering the above view points, the dispersion of NiO on alumina support by the method of hydrolysis of nickel ammino complex seems to be conducive to better activity for structure sensitive reactions. The size range of nickel oxide obtained by this procedure is also superior to that of the standard nickel oxide-alumina catalyst.

The process described in this study is feasible for preparing a catalyst where the percentage of active component is limited.

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